

Exploring the Similarities and Differences between Item Response Theory and Item-level Signal Detection Theory

William J. Muntean¹, Joseph Betts¹, and Doyoung Kim²
¹Pearson, ²NCSBN

PEARSON

Cue Recognition: Applied Experiments

Implicit Cues

Encoding Phase

Testing Phase

- No control over Encoding Phase
 - Gained through experience
- Cues are implicit and nested within stimuli
- Validated through independent evidence

Current Research

- Evaluate the usefulness of signal-detection theory in measuring cue recognition
- Compare IRT ability estimates to signal-detection estimates
 - Discriminability
 - Criterion placement
- Evaluate MR item properties through signal-detection theory

Cue Recognition: Testing and Assessment

Ecologically Representative Cues

Encoding Phase

Testing Phase

You have been referred a patient who is suspected of having a disease. What symptoms should you check for? Select all that apply.

1. Cue 1
2. Cue 2
3. Cue 3
4. Cue 4

- No control over Encoding Phase
 - Gained through studying and course preparation
- Cues represent the environment
- Validated through SMEs

Method

- 173 field-tested MR items
 - 5 to 6 response options (i.e., cues) per item
- At least 4 items (i.e., 20+ cues) randomly administered to each of 600 candidates
- Correlate SDT parameters with
 - Graded Response Model
 - Rasch Testlet Model

Signal Detection Theory

- Cues belong to two different distributions, varying in memory strength
 - Targets (valid cues)
 - Foils (invalid cues)
- Signal detection theory measures:
 - Discriminability between the two classes
 - The propensity to over/under endorse (bias)

$$P(y_{ij} = 1 | c_i, d_i, \alpha_j, \delta_j, \mathbf{X}) = \Phi(-c_i + d_i \mathbf{X} - (-\alpha_j + \delta_j \mathbf{X}))$$

Item Response Theory

- Recognizing cues is a function of a single latent trait ability
 - Item Response Functions (IRF)
- Graded Response Model:

$$P(y_{ij} \geq k | \theta_i) = \Phi(\theta_i - b_{jk})$$
- Rasch Testlet Model:

$$P(y_{ij} = 1) = \Phi(\theta_i - b_j + \gamma_{a(j)i})$$

Endorsement Bias

Graded Response Model

Testlet Model

Discriminability

Graded Response Model

Testlet Model

Signal Detection Item Characteristic Curve

Results

- Endorsement Bias
 - Candidates vary in endorsement bias but this does not correlate with abilities derived from the Graded Response Model or Rasch Testlet Model
- Discriminability
 - Surprisingly, ability estimates from both the Graded Response Model and the Rasch Testlet Model are highly correlated with SDT discriminability

Implications

- Scoring Candidates
 - Viable scoring model when both discriminability between relevant and irrelevant information and endorsement bias are important constructs